

Research Article

The Strategy of Integrating Tolerance Values into Civics Learning in Inclusive Schools

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Abstract

This study aims to: 1) Analyze the reinforcement of student's character of environmental care through the PINASA culture at senior high schools in Luwuk city. 2) Investigate the reinforcement of student's character of environmental care through PINASA culture at senior high schools in Luwuk city. 3) Identify the supporting and inhibiting factors for strengthening the character of environmental care of high school students in Luwuk city through PINASA culture. This study utilized a descriptive qualitative approach. This study uses data collection techniques in the form of observation, interviews, and documentation. Data collection with data reduction, data presentation (data display), and drawing conclusions. The results of the study show that: 1) The role of educators at senior high school in Luwuk city in strengthening the character of environmental care through PINASA culture which includes what is seen, what is heard, and what is done repeatedly. 2) The process of strengthening the student's character of environmental care through the PINASA culture in Luwuk high schools includes: class picket scheduling, the culture of managing waste properly and correctly through the PINASA culture with the 3R Program (reduce, recycle, reuse) and a culture of cleaning through the example of the school community as well as the Luwuk Banggai local government program. 3) The inhibiting and supporting factors for strengthening the character of environmental care in Luwuk high schools include: a conducive school environment such as parks, hand washing stations, trash bins, and waste banks.

Keywords: Strengthening, Environmental Care, PINASA Culture, High School Students.

Introduction

The government, through the Indonesian Ministry of National Education, has been instilling character formation through education since 2010, as stated in the national action plan for character education. Character education determined by the ministry of education consists of 18 values or characters originating from religion, Pancasila, culture and national education goals. These values or characters are religious, honest, tolerant, disciplined, hardworking, creative, independent, democratic, curious, national spirit, love of the country, respect for achievements, friendly, communicative, love of peace, like to read, care for the environment, care for the social and responsibility (Purwanti, 2017).

The lack of a waste processing system and a system for recycling non-organic waste makes the situation worse. Based on the results of a study by the Indonesian Forum for the Environment (WALHI), the fact was revealed that environmental conditions in Indonesia are increasingly threatened, especially due to infrastructure development. WALHI assesses that the ecological disaster that has occurred to date is due to the continued reduction in forest cover area and the increase in the area of critical land. WALHI reported that throughout 2014 there were 817 ecological disasters in various regions in Indonesia. This ecological disaster consisted of 608 floods, 191 landslides and 18 tidal waves which hit 5,023 villages/sub-districts and caused the death of 524 people (WALHI, 2015). The National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) recorded that between January-June 2016, there were 442 floods, 30 floods and landslides, 261 landslides, and 10 tidal waves/abrasion. The death toll resulting from this ecological disaster was 214 people. Even though there was a decrease in flood intensity from 2014, the incidence of landslides in 2016 actually increased. There are still many areas experiencing ecological disasters and the resulting loss of life, indicating that the ecosystem in Indonesia has experienced significant damage (Jayawardana, 2016).

The importance of building an environmentally caring character can be seen from the phenomenon of increasingly deteriorating waste conditions in an area, which is evidence of the local community's behavior and ignorance of the importance of good waste management. One behavior that still exists in people's lives today is the behavior of throwing rubbish carelessly.

Luwuk, a city located in Banggai Regency, Central Sulawesi Province, used to have the nickname "Water City" which means clean, safe, beautiful and neat. However, as the city of Luwuk progressed, it resulted in a significant increase in population growth, resulting in a huge impact on the waste sector which made Luwuk a "Trash City". The behavior of the people of Luwuk who still throw rubbish carelessly makes Luwuk not as beautiful and clean as before. People who live near rivers use rivers to throw away rubbish. The problem of inappropriate waste disposal in Luwuk is an illustration that people still carry out littering activities (Putri and Putro, 2015).

During the leadership of Regent Herwin Yatim and Deputy Regent Mustar Labolo in 2016, a moral movement based on local wisdom was launched in Banggai Regency, namely "PINASA" which is an abbreviation of Pia Na Sampah Ala (Saluan language), Pilee Na Sampah Ala (Balantak language) and Po Kitayo Ko Sampah Po Alayo (Banggai language). Everything means that when you see rubbish, pick it up and throw it away in the right place. This movement is very good and has a positive impact on environmental health and the health of the people of Banggai Regency. Efforts to support the "PINASA" behavior in Banggai Regency in its implementation require strategies and participation from all parties, both government, private and community through community empowerment activities (Ramli, 2016). Empowerment is basically according to Al-Anwari (2014) about enabling people to do things independently by utilizing all existing potential. Empowerment is also defined as a process to make people know, willing and able to improve their life behavior as well as a learning process in society (learning society process), especially in the health sector. In accordance with the principle of empowerment, the assistance process is gradually reduced, thereby creating an active learning society.

The mentoring process is developed as far as possible with community participation, both in planning, implementation and program evaluation. The companion's position is really just as a facilitator, whose job is to provide stimulants. The program decision-making process is still carried out by the community itself. This is intended to create a sense of ownership of the program, a sense of self-confidence and responsibility from the community. The process of awareness, empowerment and assistance must begin with the nation's next generation, which in this case is implemented from the academic world sectors. Caring for the environment is an attitude and action that always strives to prevent damage to the surrounding natural environment and develops efforts to repair natural damage that has occurred (Musarovah, 2017).

The accompanying motto of sowing seeds but not reaping is the PINASA moral movement which requires an empowerment process so that people know, want and are able to implement the PINASA behavior or movement in Banggai Regency. Based on this, the author tries to make a research contribution as a form of support for the "PINASA" moral movement. Jayawardana Research (2016) stated that the character of caring for the environment cannot be obtained instantly, but requires a long process and a relatively long time. A person will have a caring attitude towards the environment because of habits that take place continuously and sustainably. Habits (habituations) that take place continuously will be firmly embedded in the subconscious mind (subconsciousness), so that later their actions will be expressed in daily life (habits) as character values that they already have. A child who has the character of caring about the environment will have a positive impact on the survival of the environment around him. This is where the importance of efforts to prevent (mitigation) of ecological disasters from an early age.

Another research is Ramli's research (2016) who suggested that the regional government continue to maintain and also improve the process of socializing and providing information about PINASA to increase knowledge by paying attention to social culture and local wisdom such as language, customs and religion in the Banggai Regency community. It is necessary to formulate messages in socialization that include the "dangers" or negative consequences that will arise if the PINASA moral movement is not carried out, so as to create a positive attitude and inspire people to tend to take action, especially the PINASA movement. The government and society are trying together to provide facilities in accordance with their respective authorities and capabilities. The government provides as many communal waste bins as possible and regulates the transportation and management of waste as best as possible, while the community provides rubbish bins in their respective households to make it easier to live a clean and healthy life by throwing rubbish in the right place. It is important to instill a sense of awareness and concern for environmental

cleanliness in society, especially children, because children are the nation's future young generation. If the problem of littering is ingrained in children, it is very dangerous for the future because children are formed from what is instilled in them from childhood (Bafadhol, 2017). Strengthening caring character can be done at school through the role of teachers and other school members.

PINASA culture has been taught and socialized to students in Banggai Regency in schools, but in reality there are still many young people and people who still have little awareness of throwing rubbish in its place and it still makes the environment dirty. This is proven by the amount of waste generated in the city of Luwuk increasing from year to year. Based on data from the Department of Human Settlements and Spatial Planning, the amount of waste produced by each household and the limited capacity of transportation infrastructure, it is very possible that waste that is not transported to the landfill will be scattered into landfills, waterways, rivers and empty land or burned (Farhatilwardah *et al.*, 2019).

In this research, we analyze the role of educators in Luwuk city high schools in strengthening students' environmentally caring character through PINASA culture, and identify the supporting and inhibiting factors that exist during the process of building environmentally caring character through PINASA culture in schools. Character is one of the elements taught in Pancasila and citizenship education lessons at school. This research will identify and analyze the results of educators' efforts to strengthen environmentally caring character through PINASA culture in students.

Research Method

This research is a qualitative descriptive research. This research describes the strengthening of students' environmentally caring character towards PINASA culture in high schools throughout the city of Luwuk. This is in accordance with opinion (Sugiyono, 2016) which suggests that there are several terms used in qualitative research, namely naturalistic or naturalistic research or inquiry, ethnography, symbolic interactionism, inward perspective, ethnomethodology, the Chicago school, phenomenological, case study, interpretative, ecological, and descriptive. This research was conducted at senior high schools in the city of Luwuk, Banggai Regency, Central Sulawesi Province, including: Senior High Schools of Luwuk Banggai City, Santo Yoseph Catholic High School and Muhammadiyah High School. This research was conducted with the aim of introducing PINASA culture to all Indonesian society.

The data and information needed are in accordance with the research objectives that the researcher is carrying out in collecting data related to the completeness of the data to be researched, so two types of data are needed, namely primary data and secondary data, these data include:

1. Primary Data

Primary data is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors (Sugiyono, 2016). The primary data that will be obtained by researchers is:

- a) Results of interviews with school/madrasah principals, regarding the general description of high schools in the city of Luwuk (history of establishment, geographical location, vision and mission, condition of students, teachers and staff, and infrastructure) and the efforts of principals and teachers in forming a caring character environment for students through PINASA culture.
- b) The results of interviews with students regarding the efforts made by the school principal or class teacher in forming environmentally caring characters in students through PINASA culture.

2. Secondary Data

Secondary data is a data source that does not directly provide data to data collectors, for example through other people or through documents, for example data from magazines, newspapers, statements or other publications (Sugiyono, 2016). In this case, the data is taken from the following general description of high school schools in Luwuk city:

- a) History and geographic,
- b) Facilities and infrastructure,
- c) Organizational structure,
- d) Condition of teachers, administration and students.

Researchers used data collection techniques in the form of observation, interviews and documentation. Data collection techniques are methods that researchers can use to collect data. According to Sugiyono (2016) stated that in qualitative research, data collection techniques are carried out by observation, interviews, questionnaires, documentation, and a combination of the four. The data collected by researchers from this

research is needed for data analysis and is continued by conducting data examination. In this research, triangulation was used. Triangulation means researchers use different data collection techniques to obtain data from the same source (Sugiyono, 2016).

Researchers classified data that had been obtained in high schools throughout the city of Luwuk regarding the implementation of PINASA culture which can shape students' environmentally caring character and described the role of school principals and teachers in implementing PINASA culture. Conclusions in qualitative research are new findings that have not previously existed. Conclusions are made with existing data and are different from previous research. This research uses a type of case study research with why and how questions to find out and describe the strategies used by religious leaders of Raas sub-district in increasing the participation of Raas sub-district communities in the Sumenep district head elections. This research was conducted in Raas sub-district, Sumenep district.

Researchers took this location because religious leaders in this location (Raas sub-district) are influential in increasing community participation in the Sumenep district head elections. The Raas sub-district community is still very trusting of the words and seduction of religious leaders, so it is necessary to find out what strategies are used by the Raas sub-district religious shop in seducing the Raas sub-district community to be active in the Sumenep district head election. This research data is taken directly from the research location, namely in the Raas sub-district of the Sumenep district. The location is suitable to be used as a research site, because religious leaders in the sub-district still have great potential in increasing community participation in the Sumenep district head election.

Research Results and Discussion

Character education that cares about the environment has become an obligation for every school because it is one of the 18 characters formulated by the government. However, environmental problems caused by human activities give rise to questions to what extent environmentally caring character education has been carried out through educational institutions. This needs to be studied together and it is important to provide case studies regarding the implementation of environmentally caring character education that has succeeded in bringing about change. Implementation of character education can be done through integration in subjects through Learning Implementation Plans (RPP) and syllabi; integration in local content; self-development activities in the form of acculturation and habituation (including conditioning, routine activities, spontaneous activities, role models, programmed activities); extracurricular; counseling guidance (Hafida and Wahid, 2018).

Implementation of character education that cares about the environment can also be done through integrating programs into the learning process through developing syllabi and lesson plans, self-development activities which consist of habits and school culture (Purwanti, 2017). The higher education curriculum development by every university must refer to a national standard curriculum that covers intelligence, morals, and skill development. In civic education as its main purpose is to develop good citizenship who internalize and actualize Pancasila, it must take this responsibility in daily life. Thus, students who have learned civics at university are hoping to be smart, skilled, faithful, and fully devoted to Indonesia as a nation. Those values should be reflected in thinking habits and acting according (Chotimah *et al.*, 2021).

The role of educators in developing character in this research refers to the theory of Cheesman *et al.*, (2020) that the effect of preoperative education on opioid consumption in patients undergoing treatment is about developing character through what is seen, what is heard, and what is done repeatedly. An environment that supports children's good behavior on an ongoing basis will shape good character in children. Habits of good behavior need to be instilled in the nation's young generation. Educators, principals, teachers and staff at Senior High Schools of Luwuk Banggai City, Catholic High School and Muhammadiyah Luwuk High School have become role models for students in forming environmentally caring characters. This example is in accordance with the teacher's role as a role model and mentor for students (Marisyah *et al.*, 2019). In this case, the principal's role is to mobilize, coordinate and harmonize all educational resources, including the school's relationship with the community (Mulyasa, 2018). School as a place to realize educational character should be a comfortable and inspiring place for students, teachers, and education staff to learn. The various strategies needed to build attitudes and habituations in school reflect Pancasila values. They should be part of each school's learning process and culture (Chotimah *et al.*, 2022). Exemplary performance is shown starting from the school principal, teachers and staff. The principal's example is demonstrated through discipline and militancy in his leadership. This

example can be seen from the attitude of teachers who always maintain cleanliness by throwing rubbish in the right place and the involvement of teachers in managing the school environment.

Teachers at Senior High Schools of Luwuk Banggai City, Catholic High School and Muhammadiyah Luwuk High School also took part in collecting rubbish, cleaning the school and arranging the park. In the Clean Friday activity, the teacher took part in planting flowers and arranging the garden. In waste management, teachers also intervene directly by participating in composting and making handicrafts together with students. The character of caring for the environment does not only occur between teachers and students or parents and children, but between leaders who are able to change their subordinates to then set an example for their students. In essence, environmental awareness programs can be carried out by all schools in order to carry out the school's task of forming an environmentally caring character. But without example, this program cannot run optimally and touch its essence. The program carried out by the regional government for PINASA culture can run well and be sustainable because there is a figure who is looked up to by all school members, namely the school principal through the example he provides. These findings confirm that school principals play an important role in the success of character education (Mulyasa, 2018). Senior High Schools of Luwuk Banggai City, Santo Yoseph Catholic High School and SMA Muhammadiyah Luwuk also show that the role of school leaders is able to change not only the environmentally caring character but also become a motivation in strengthening the environmentally caring character of students through PINASA culture for schools other.

Character education is one part that is implemented in educational institutions (schools). The formal education environment (school) is one place to instill education based on values in accordance with Pancasila. The reason why school is one of the places to develop character education is because it includes learning, guidance and giving strength to one's beliefs. Character development by PPKn (Pancasila and Citizenship Education) teachers is very appropriate because character is also described and taught in this subject. Apart from that, PPKn lessons have a reference for developing the morality of each student so that they can become good citizens, so it can be said that PPKn lessons have a big and important contribution in improving the morality of the nation's next generation or can prevent juvenile delinquency. Character education and civics are two mutually important subjects in character education. Apart from that, civics lessons have a reference for developing the morality of each student so that they can become good citizens. So that civics subjects have a contribution to preventing juvenile delinquency. This research refers to Roesminingsih and Lamijan's theory (2015) about the roles that are considered the most dominant and classified. First, the teacher as a demonstrator who masters the material or subject matter he will teach and continually develops it in the sense of improving his abilities in terms of the knowledge he has because this will greatly determine the learning outcomes achieved by students. Second, the teacher as a corrector can differentiate or sort out good and bad grades. Values and norms are two concepts that really must be implemented in the social sphere. Good values and norms must always be maintained by educators or teachers because teaching is a profession that has a big role in cultivating a civilized spirit or character.

Basically, every teacher has to motivate students during learning; it is not only the job of civics teachers to motivate students in teaching and learning activities. The teacher introduces the character of caring for the environment through PINASA culture to students who show an attitude of indifference to themselves. This fact was known to researchers, because previously they had made observations at Senior High Schools of Luwuk Banggai City, Catholic High School and Muhammadiyah Luwuk High School. The process of developing teacher character can use various methods through their role, namely by providing verbal and non-verbal motivation, providing positive and negative reinforcement. In this way, students will get used to good behavior, be able to appreciate existing differences, respect teachers, carry out active learning activities, and so on. This is because teachers also use punishment as negative reinforcement so that students who engage in negative behavior do not repeat it (Handiyarno, 2016). Reinforcement is a consequence that increases the probability that a behavior will occur. In contrast, punishment is a consequence that reduces the probability of a behavior occurring (Sudrajat *et al.*, 2020).

The role of civic education teachers is as the most important and main motivator in the interactive process of learning in the classroom because the classroom is a gathering place for all students and teachers to gain knowledge. Learning can be said to be effective and smooth, when class conditions can be managed well by the teacher and students and as a motivator, the teacher encourages students to be able to implement the character of caring for the environment in each student because educational interaction is not impossible if there is one among the students who doesn't care about the environment and responsibility for the pickets given. In developing environmentally caring character in students, PPKn teachers use several methods,

namely by providing verbal and non-verbal motivation. Verbal character development is by providing motivation, advice, stories, praise, reprimands and punishment, while non-verbal methods are by habituating behavior and setting an example. Character development through verbal and non-verbal motivation has the aim of reducing violations or deviant student behavior in class and outside of class in order to create comfortable and safe classroom and school conditions. This research refers to Yahya's opinion (2019) regarding the process of strengthening the character of caring for the environment can be formed in various ways at school, namely: First, making a class picket schedule. Students are given reinforcement about the importance of a clean environment. Second, the culture of managing waste properly and correctly by cultivating the habit of reducing plastic use. Third, a culture of cleanliness. The following is a complete explanation.

a) Class Picket Schedule

The class picket schedule is made by the class cleanliness section at the beginning of each year. Students are given reinforcement about the importance of a clean environment. The new class picket schedule will run effectively within the next month. Every child who is scheduled is aware that after prayer they must immediately complete their task (Yahya, 2019). Luwuk City High School teachers organize daily cleaning pickets consisting of students. This picket is tasked with cleaning classrooms during the day after school hours and in the morning before class starts. Every morning, starting from the moment students enter the school gate, students are accustomed to paying attention to the cleanliness of their surrounding environment.

If there is rubbish that is out of place, students are required to pick it up and throw it in the rubbish bin. To strengthen this habit, the school implements the PINASA (piana trash style) program in every school activity. Every student and teacher is required to pick up rubbish that is out of place and then throw it in the rubbish bin. The school's hope is that this habit becomes a culture for all school members wherever they are. The estuary of the educational process is changes in student behavior for the better (Marisyah *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, in forming students' environmentally caring character through PINASA culture at senior high schools throughout Luwuk city, it is not only about providing understanding or knowledge about the environment and responsibility, but also the formation of habits or behavior.

b) Culture of Managing Waste Properly and Correctly

Culture managing waste properly and correctly by making it a habit to reduce the use of plastic because plastic waste is difficult to decompose, throwing rubbish in its place, dividing waste according to its categories, dry waste and wet waste, rubbish that can be recycled and rubbish that cannot be recycled and making a habit of picking up rubbish strewn across the street Friday (Yahya, 2019). In this research, Senior High Schools of Luwuk Banggai City in its clean Friday activities, Senior High Schools of Luwuk Banggai City implemented the 3R program (reduce, recycle, reuse). In reduce activities; schools reduce the use of plastic by providing gallons of drinking water in each class. This is to reduce the use of plastic through bottled mineral water. Apart from that, schools also prohibit the sale of plastic wrapped food in school canteens.

Implementation of school used items such as used paint cans, used buckets, used tires and single-use plastic drinking bottles. This item is reused into waste baskets and flower pots. In the context of recycling, schools recycle organic and non-organic waste. The school manages organic waste into fertilizer and compost. Meanwhile, non-organic waste such as plastic is recycled into handicrafts. Examples are table flowers, baskets and wall decorations. In daily activities, Senior High Schools of Luwuk Banggai City, Catholic High School and Muhammadiyah Luwuk High School also carry out spontaneous activities through PINASA culture, including invitations, warnings, punishments and rewards.

c) Clean Culture

A culture of cleaning carried out by school principals, teachers, students and cleaning staff in the school environment (Yahya, 2019). A culture of cleaning to form and strengthen students' and teachers' concern for the environment is carried out by Senior High Schools of Luwuk Banggai City, Catholic High School and Muhammadiyah Luwuk High School with several activities carried out regularly. Teachers can also implement a culture of cleaning by always inviting students to throw away rubbish in the right place and pick up rubbish that is not in the right place. When teachers see students throwing rubbish out of place or being indifferent when they see the environment in a dirty condition, they will be given an immediate warning and punishment in the form of cleaning the school outside of the picket schedule. The process of strengthening the character of caring for the environment through school culture can be through adiwiyata activities which are directed at creating school institutions that care about and have an environmental

culture for schools. School principals, teachers, and employees as school members also play a role in understanding and providing examples of behavior that shows the value of caring for the environment to students. Students have a tendency to imitate what the adults around them do, as in the expression children see children do (Nurizka *et al.*, 2020).

Supporting factors for strengthening character education refer to the opinion of Ronen *et al.*, (2016) including: strategic location and a conducive school environment so as to create a pleasant learning atmosphere, collaboration between teachers and stakeholders in creating closeness with students. Supporting facilities in strengthening students' environmentally caring character through PINASA culture at Luwuk City Senior High Schools are equipped with hygiene support facilities such as providing separate bins for organic and inorganic waste. Apart from that, the school also provides cleaning equipment such as brooms, mops, dusters and buckets. At several points the school displays the PINASA culture slogan and contains recommendations for managing the environment well. Factors that hinder the strengthening of character, including the character of caring for the environment, in this research refer to the opinion of Farhatilwardah *et al.*, (2019) regarding external and internal factors, external factors include some students' family or community environments that do not support the students, in the sense that the students' parents are busy with their own activities, there are those who work abroad, the students only stay at home with their grandmother or grandfather, so students lack of attention from parents.

Conclusions

Based on the results of research and discussions related to strengthening the environmentally caring character of students through Pinasa culture in high schools throughout Luwuk city, the following conclusions can be drawn.

- 1) The role of educators in Luwuk city high schools in strengthening environmentally caring character through PINASA culture about developing character through what is seen, what is heard, and what is done repeatedly. The structure and role of educators in introducing environmentally caring character education, getting used to environmentally caring character activities, role models in instilling environmentally caring character education in students in carrying out PINASA cultural activities.
- 2) The process of strengthening students' environmentally caring character through PINASA culture at Luwuk city high schools which includes: making class picket schedules according to schedule, a culture of managing waste properly and correctly through PINASA culture with the 3R Program (reduce, recycle, reuse) and by promote a culture of reducing the use of plastic and a culture of cleanliness through the example of school residents and also the Luwuk Banggai regional government program.
- 3) Supporting factors for strengthening environmentally caring character in Luwuk city senior high schools include: strategic location and a conducive school environment so as to create a pleasant learning atmosphere such as a garden, hand washing place in front of the class, trash cans in each in front of the class, and there is a waste bank, cooperation between teachers and stakeholders in creating closeness with students, while the inhibiting factors for strengthening environmentally caring character in Luwuk city high schools are internal and external factors, including: internal factors such as within the students themselves who have not been able to apply encouraging discipline within their own students and there are still students who are still not aware of the importance of keeping the environment clean, that is, there are still students who are lazy about throwing rubbish in its place so that the desk drawer becomes their favorite place to store their rubbish, whereas external factors are some of the student's family or community environment which has not supported the student because the student's parents are busy in their own activities, so the student lacks attention from their parents. This obstacle can be overcome with awareness of students and parents as well as examples from educators about the importance of strengthening students' environmentally caring character.

Declarations

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References

1. Al-Anwari, A.M. 2014. Strategy for building environmentally caring character in independent adiwiyata schools. *Ta'dib*, 19(2): 227-252.
2. Bafadhol, I. 2017. Moral education from an Islamic perspective. *Journal of Islamic Education*, 6(12): 45–61.
3. Cheesman, Q., DeFrance, M., Stenson, J., Weekes, D., Feldman, J., Abboud, J. and Austin, L. 2020. The effect of preoperative education on opioid consumption in patients undergoing arthroscopic rotator cuff repair: A prospective, randomized clinical trial-2-year follow-up. *Journal of Shoulder and Elbow Surgery*, 29(9): 1743-1750.
4. Chotimah, U., Kurnisar, K., Ermanovida, E. and Juainah, N. 2021. Building religion, honesty, discipline and student curiosity characters in online HOTS-based citizenship education learning. *Civics Journal: Civic Studies Media*, 18(1): 118–126.
5. Chotimah, U., Yanzi, H., Kurnisar, K., Faisal, E.El., Yusuf, M. and Susanti, E. 2022. Strengthening students' character through TPACK-based learning. *Journal of Civics: Media Studies in Citizenship*, 19(2): 235–244.
6. Farhatilwardah, F., Hastuti, D. and Krisnatuti, D. 2019. Character of adolescent manners: The influence of parental socialization methods and self-control. *Journal of Family and Consumer Sciences*, 12(2), 114-125.
7. Hafida, N. and Wahid, A.H. 2018. Formation of caring character and environmental culture for students in madrasas through the adiwiyata program. *Phycrotuna*, 8(2): 950-971.
8. Handiyarno, Y.D. 2016. Improving social care attitude and social study achievement through action learning and video media learning strategies in class IV SDN 1 Pelumutan Kemangkong district. Doctoral Dissertation, Muhammadiyah University Purwokerto.
9. Jayawardana, H.B.A. 2016. Character education that cares about the environment from an early age as an effort to mitigate ecological disasters. *Proceedings of Symbion (Symposium on Biology Education)*, (Vol. 5726, pp. 49-64).
10. Marisyah, A., Firman, F. and Rusdinal, R. 2019. Ki Hadjar Dewantara's thoughts about education. *Tambusai Education Journal*, 33(11): 2-6.
11. Mulyasa, H.E. 2018. *Character education management*. 1st Edition: Literary Earth.
12. Musarovah, E. 2017. Reinforcing Pancasila values to young generation as a true national identity. *Ministry of Defense Information Media*, 68: 1–31.
13. Nurizka, R., Irawan, R., Sakti, S.A. and Hidayat, L. 2020. Internalization of school culture to foster awareness of Pancasila values in elementary school students. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(10), 4818–4825.
14. Purwanti, D. 2017. Environmental care character education and its implementation. *Dwijia Cendekia: Pedagogical Research Journal*, 1(2): 14–20.
15. Putri, A. and Putro, H. 2015. Study of the relationship between factors that shape community behavior towards waste disposal patterns in Luwuk. *Journal of Regional and Urban Planning*, 4(2): 419-27.
16. Ramli, R. 2016. Community empowerment in clean and healthy living behavior (PHBS) through the moral movement "PINASA" in Banggai district. Faculty of Public Health, Tompotika University Luwuk.
17. Roesminingsih and Lamijan, S.H. 2015. *Educational theory and practice*. Surabaya: Bintang Surabaya.
18. Ronen, T., Hamama, L., Rosenbaum, M. and Mishely-Yarlap, A. 2016. Subjective well-being in adolescence: The role of self-control, social support, age, gender, and familial crisis. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 17(1): 81–104.
19. Sudrajat, T., Hasanah, A., Sangga, U., Bandung, B., Islam, U., Sunan, N. and Djati, G. 2020. Pancasila values and national civilization: Policy conception and implementation. *Moderate Journal*, 6: 857–867.

20. Sugiyono. 2016. Quantitative, qualitative and R and D research methods. Alfabeta.
21. WALHI. 2015. The 2015 environmental review, making promises demanding change. Indonesian Forum for the Environment.
22. Yahya, M. S. 2019. Integration of environmental care character education in learning activities at Sdit Imam Syafi'i Petanahan Kebumen. *Insania: Journal of Alternative Thought in Education*, 24(2): 232-246.

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